

Modelling Decarbonization Pathways¹ in the Power Sector in Developing Countries: The Case of Dominican Republic

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Context

- Dominican Republic sets renewable energy targets of 25% by law and a government goal of 30% by 2030.
- NDC for 27% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050.
- Challenges to reaching short-term goal: increasing electricity demand, government reliance on conventional energy plants.

Source: OC, 2024

Research questions:

- What is the *required scale* of renewable energy installation by 2030 to achieve goal of 30% electricity production from renewables?
- How to reach *carbon neutrality* by 2050, considering *increasing demand* for energy and current reliance on conventional energy plants?

Scenarios

Scenario Name	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
BAU	No carbon target	Historical trends remain. Includes reaching 30% of generation from RE 2030. No emissions reduction target.
NET-ZERO	Net zero by 2050	All technologies available. Linear reduction of fossil power plants' activity from 2035 until 2050. Linear reduction of CO2 emissions from 2030 until 2050.
RE-50%-RESTR	Net zero by 2050, with conservative RE potential	All technologies available. Linear reduction of fossil power plants' activity from 2035 until 2050. Linear reduction of CO2 emissions from 2030 until 2050. <u>RE potential halved.</u>

Electricity Annual Generation - Results (1/5)

Total Installed Capacity - Results (2/5)

Total Discounted Costs - Results (3/5)

Fuel Imports - Results (4/5)

Total Annual Emissions - Results (5/5)

Policy Insights

- The 30-30 goal ***has no impact*** on emissions reduction by 2050. A more **ambitious** target could be established.
- **3 times** the BAU installed capacity, mainly **PV** and **Wind**, is necessary to achieve Net-Zero by 2050.
- The Net-Zero scenario **increases** *energy sovereignty* and **lowers** the system's variable costs, while achieving total electrification of the end-user demand.

Title: Emissions by source for all scenarios

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Thank You!